

1. INTRODUCTION

K. Schwarzschild was the first to apply Einstein's general relativity to the problem of a static, spherically symmetric space-time [1]. In the second of his papers, he was able to obtain the pressure as well as the metric inside a sphere of perfect fluid of constant density; cf. Refs. [2] and [3], as well as books on general relativity for a derivation and discussion using a more transparent, convenient notation.

In a previous paper [4], hereafter referred to as I, building on the framework of the general theory of relativity (GR) and two conservation laws, the author derived a set of exact equations for the energy density and metric inside a sphere of perfect, non-rotating fluid (constituting the so-called 'Interior Schwarzschild problem'). For a given mass M and finite radius R of the sphere, the equations allow one to solve for the energy density, $\mathcal{E}(r)$, the pressure, $p(r)$, the metric and other quantities as a function of the radial coordinate, r .

Starting from basic relations of GR, a detailed step by step derivation of the equations is given in I. The paper also proved the consistency of the equations with the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff (TOV) equation [5], and with an exact equation due to S. Weinberg (Ref [5], Eq. (11.6.14)). Since the equations derived in I are nonlinear, an approximate solution was presented for selected values of the compactness parameter, $2GM/c^2 r$ (corresponding to those pertaining to neutron stars).

The purpose of this paper is to present again and summarize the exact equations obtained in I in Sections 2 and 3, leaving aside their derivation and other topics discussed in I. In addition, Section 4 presents proofs of consistency of the equations with two further exact relations known from GR theory. For convenience and easy reference, all four of the consistency relations are included in Section 4. The complete agreement with the equations derived in I (presented in Secs. 2 and 3) thus further cements the validity of the latter

To make this paper reasonably self-contained, we begin in Sec. 2 by briefly recalling some basic relations and establishing the notation.

2. BRIEF RECALL OF SOME BASIC RELATIONS

We are considering a non-rotating sphere of perfect fluid in static equilibrium, for which the metric is described by the space-time line element

$$ds^2 = e^{\nu} c^2 dt^2 - e^{\lambda} dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2), \quad (2.1)$$

where r, θ, φ are the space-like coordinates, t is a time-like coordinate and c is the velocity of light in vacuum. The static spherical symmetry implies that ν and λ are functions only of the radial coordinate r : $\nu = \nu(r)$, $\lambda = \lambda(r)$. The only non-vanishing components of the energy-momentum tensor T_{α}^{β} are

$$T_0^0 = \mathcal{E}(r), \quad (2.2a)$$

$$T_1^1 = T_2^2 = T_3^3 = -p(r), \quad (2.2b)$$